

INTERACTION OF THIONYL CHLORIDE AND AROMATIC HYDROXY
KETONES AND THEIR DERIVATIVES IN PRESENCE OF FINELY
DIVIDED COPPER. PART X. PREPARATION OF 3:3'-DI-
BENZOYL-2:6-2':6'- AND -4:6-4':6'-TETRAHYDROXY-
DIPHENYL THIOETHERS AND THEIR DERIVATIVES

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Preparation of 3:3'-dibenzoyl-2:6-2':6'-tetrahydroxydiphenyl thioether (I) and 3:3'-dibenzoyl-4:6-4':6'-tetrahydroxydiphenyl thioether (II) is described. Bromination of (I) in acetic acid medium affords 3:3'-dibenzoyl-4:6-2':5-tetrahydroxy-5:5'-dibromodiphenyl thioether and of (II) yields 3:3'-dibenzoyl-4:6-4':6'-tetrahydroxy-5:5'-dibromodiphenyl thioether. Both these dibromothioethers furnish the same 2:4-dihydroxy-3-bromo-5-nitrobenzophenone on treatment with nitric acid. Their tetra-acetyl, dimethyl and tetramethyl derivatives as well as 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazones have been prepared.

The investigation reported in this communication is in continuation of Part VIII of this series (this *Journal*, 1956, 33, 440). 2:4-Dihydroxybenzophenone, when treated with thionyl chloride and copper in presence of chloroform at room temperature, furnishes two thioethers—(I), soluble and (II), insoluble in chloroform. Bromination in presence of acetic acid affords different bromo-thioethers, viz., (VI) and (XIII) respectively, which yield the same 2:4-dihydroxy-3-bromo-5-nitrobenzophenone (VIII). This points out that bromine in (VI) undergoes migration during the interaction with nitric acid. Such a migration is known in the case of the nitration of 4:6-dibromoresorcinol-3-benzoate (Hodgson and Dyson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 946). Similar migration of bromine has been observed by the present authors in the case of the action of nitric acid on 2,4-dihydroxy-5-bromobenzophenone, when the bromo-nitro derivative obtained is found different from the bromination product of 2:4-dihydroxy-3-nitrobenzophenone, but identical with the bromination product of 2:4-dihydroxy-5-nitrobenzophenone (under publication in the *Journal of the University of Bombay*).

Bromination with an excess of bromine solution and heating for some time on a boiling water-bath furnished 2:4-dihydroxy-3:5-dibromobenzophenone in the case of both the thioethers. These experiments throw no light on the constitution of the thioethers.

The thioether obtained from 2:4-dihydroxy-5-bromobenzophenone by the action of sulphur dichloride is found to be identical with the dibromo derivative of (I), and hence, it is assigned the constitution 3:3'-dibenzoyl-2:6-2':6'-tetrahydroxydiphenyl thioether.

There are two possible positions where the two nuclei can be linked through the sulphur atom. These are *meta* to the ketonic group and *ortho* to both the hydroxy groups or *ortho* to one hydroxy group and *para* to the other, i. e. 3 or 5 respectively. The thioether (II) should therefore be 3:3'-dibenzoyl-4:6-4':6'-tetrahydroxydiphenyl thioether.

Further, it is found that from 2-hydroxy-4-methoxybenzophenone, only one thioether is obtained by the action of thionyl chloride and copper, and this is found to be identical with 3:3'-dibenzoyl-4:4'-dihydroxy-6:6'-dimethoxydiphenyl thioether obtained by methylation of (II).

That the mechanism of the thioether formation from thionyl chloride and copper is due to the intermediate formation of sulphur monochloride and sulphur dichloride *in situ*, as reported by Hirwe, Jadhav and Chakradeo (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 57, 101), is supported in the present work by the fact that the thioether (I) is formed by the interaction of 2:4-dihydroxybenzophenone and sulphur monochloride, whereas the thioether (II) is formed when it is allowed to react with sulphur dichloride.

EXPERIMENTAL

3:3'-Dibenzoyl-2:6-2':6'-tetrahydroxydiphenyl Thioether (I).—Thionyl chloride (9 c. c.) was gradually added (over half an hour) to the cooled suspension of 2:4-dihydroxybenzophenone (13 g.) and copper powder (6 g.) in dry chloroform (100 c. c.). The reaction mixture was left for 36 hours at room temperature and then filtered and the residue washed several times with dry chloroform. A yellow sticky solid was left behind after removal of chloroform (room temperature). It was first washed with petroleum ether (b.p. 40°-60°) and then treated with benzene to remove stickiness. The solid, thus formed, was treated with a little alcohol and then crystallised from acetic acid in tiny, pale yellow needles; m. p. 246-47°, yield 1 g. (Found: S, 7.0. $C_{26}H_{18}O_6S$ requires S, 6.99 per cent).

It develops a purple coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride solution. This thioether (I) was also obtained when dry ethereal solution of 2:4-dihydroxybenzophenone (2g. in 40 c. c.), cooled in ice, was treated with sulphur monochloride (2 c. c.) and the reaction was allowed to proceed for 1 hour at that temperature. The paste remaining after removal of the ether (room temperature) was boiled with water, when it solidified. It was extracted with alcohol and the solid obtained from alcohol on evaporation was crystallised from acetic acid in pale yellow needles, m. p. 246-47°, yield 1 g.

3:3'-Dibenzoyl-4:6-4':6'-tetrahydroxydiphenyl Thioether (II).—The chloroform-insoluble portion in the above experiment was repeatedly boiled with HCl (dil.) to remove cuprous chloride. The residue was finally crystallised from acetic acid in yellow needles, m. p. 236-37°, yield 5 g. (Found: C, 67.8; H, 4.0; S, 7.3. $C_{26}H_{18}O_6S$ requires C, 68.1; H, 3.9; S, 6.99 per cent).

This is more soluble in alcohol and acetic acid than the thioether (I). It also develops a purple coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride.

The thioether (II) was also formed when sulphur dichloride (1 c. c.) was added to the well-cooled solution of 2:4-dihydroxybenzophenone (2 g.) in dry ether (40 c. c.). The reaction mixture was kept for 1 hour at room temperature. A yellow paste remained behind when ether was removed (room temperature). It afforded a solid

when treated with petroleum ether (40°-60°). It was then treated with benzene and finally crystallised from acetic acid in yellow needles, m. p. 236-37°, yield 0.5 g.

The *tetra-acetyl derivative* (III) of the thioether (I) was obtained by its acetylation with acetic anhydride in presence of a few drops of pyridine and heating the mixture on a boiling water-bath for half an hour. It crystallised from dilute alcohol in colorless needles, m. p. 121-22°. (Found: S, 5.4. $C_{24}H_{24}O_{10}S$ requires S, 5.1 per cent).

6:6-Dimethyl derivative (IV) of the thioether (I) was formed when 0.5g. of it was heated on a boiling water-bath for 10 hours with dimethyl sulphate (0.25 c. c.) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (1 g.) in presence of dry acetone. The solid obtained from acetone solution was crystallised from alcohol (charcoal) in shining needles, m.p. 181-82°. (Found: C, 68.8; H, 4.3; S, 6.4. $C_{22}H_{22}O_4S$ requires C, 69.13; H, 4.52; S, 6.58 per cent).

Tetramethyl derivative (V) of the thioether (I) was formed when the thioether (I) was heated with more dimethyl sulphate. The solid obtained from acetone solution was first heated with 5% NaOH solution and then crystallised from alcohol in colorless needles, m. p. 159-60°. (Found: C, 69.8; H, 4.9; S, 6.5. $C_{20}H_{20}O_4S$ requires C, 70.03; H, 5.06; S, 6.2 per cent).

2:4-Dinitrophenylhydrazone of (I) was obtained in dark red needles from acetic acid, m. p. 210-11° (decomp.). (Found: N, 14.1. $C_{16}H_{12}O_{12}N_2S$ requires N, 13.7 per cent).

5:5'-Dibromo derivative (VI) of (I) was obtained when (I:0.9 g.) was suspended in hot acetic acid (10 c. c.) and bromine solution in acetic acid (3.2 c. c. of 20%, w/v) was gradually added to it. A white product separated which was crystallised from acetic acid in colorless needles, m.p. 220-21°. (Found: Br, 25.8. $C_{26}H_{16}O_4Br_2S$ requires Br, 25.97 per cent).

2:4-Dihydroxy-5-bromobenzophenone was obtained when a solution of bromine in acetic acid (15 c. c. of 20%, w/v) was added to the suspension of 2:4-dihydroxybenzophenone (4.3 g.) in acetic acid (5 c. c.) and the reaction mixture left overnight at room temperature and then diluted. The solid obtained was crystallised from dilute alcohol in colorless needles, m. p. 148-49°. (Found: Br, 27.5. $C_{18}H_{10}O_3Br$ requires Br, 27.3 per cent).

The same thioether (VI) was also obtained from 2:4-dihydroxy-5-bromobenzophenone when sulphur dichloride (1 c. c.) was added to its ice-cooled solution in dry ether (1g. in 20 c. c.) and the mixture was left at room temperature for 1 hour. When the ether was removed (room temperature), a semi-solid was obtained which was first washed with low-boiling petroleum ether and then extracted with alcohol. The solid obtained on removal of alcohol was crystallised from acetic acid, m. p. 220-21°. No depression was observed when mixed m. p. with (VI) was taken,

2:4-Dihydroxy-3:5-dibromobenzophenone (VII).—The thioether (I:0.5g.), suspended in acetic acid (5 c. c.), was mixed with bromine solution in acetic acid (1 c. c. in 25 c. c.) and heated on a boiling water-bath for 4 hours. When diluted with some

water a crystalline solid separated which was crystallised from dilute alcohol in white needles, m. p. 150-51°. (Found: Br, 42.8. $C_{13}H_9O_3Br_2$ requires Br, 43.0 per cent). It showed no lowering in m. p. with the genuine specimen prepared by treating the suspension of 2:4-dihydroxybenzophenone (2 g.) in acetic acid (5 c. c.) with acetic acid solution of bromine (2.5 c. c. in 25 c. c. of acid) and leaving the mixture overnight at room temperature. Crystals that had separated were filtered, washed and crystallised from dilute alcohol in white needles, m. p. 150-51°. (Found: Br, 42.8. $C_{13}H_9O_3Br_2$ requires Br, 43.0 per cent).

The thioether (II) also afforded the same dibromo derivative (VII) with bromine solution under similar conditions.

2:4-Dihydroxy-3-bromo-5-nitrobenzophenone (VIII).—Nitric acid (d 1.4, 5 c.c.) was gradually added to an ice-cooled suspension of the dibromo-thioether (VI: 1 g.) in acetic acid (10 c. c.). It was left at room temperature for about one hour and then poured over crushed ice. The solid obtained was crystallised from acetic acid in yellow plates, m. p. 208-209°. (Found: Br, 23.5. $C_{13}H_9O_6NBr$ requires Br, 23.7 per cent). It showed no lowering in m. p. with the genuine specimen prepared (*vide infra*).

The same thioether (VIII) was formed by the action of nitric acid on the thioether (XIII) under identical conditions.

Tetra-acetyl derivative (IX) of the thioether (II) was obtained from thioether (II) in the same way as (III) was obtained from (I). It crystallised from dilute alcohol in shining, colorless, rhombic plates, m. p. 146-47°. (Found: S, 5.3. $C_{24}H_{20}O_{10}S$ requires S, 5.1 per cent).

6:6'-Dimethyl derivative (X) of the thioether (II) was prepared and crystallised in the same way as (IV) was obtained from (I), m.p. 182-83°. (Found: C, 68.9; H, 4.3; S, 6.3. $C_{24}H_{22}O_6S$ requires C, 69.13; H, 4.52; S, 6.58 per cent). It developed a bottle-green colour with alcoholic ferric chloride.

The same thioether (X) was prepared from 2-hydroxy-4-methoxybenzophenone in the same way as thioether (I). The pasty mass obtained from chloroform solution was boiled with water, after treatment with petroleum ether (40°-60°), when it solidified. It was finally crystallised from alcohol in yellow plates, m. p. 182-83°, yield 2 g. from 4.5 g. of the ketone.

2-Hydroxy 4-methoxybenzophenone furnished (X) on treatment with sulphur monochloride or sulphur dichloride also under similar condition as (I) was prepared from 2:4-dihydroxybenzophenone; yield 1 g. from 4 g.

The *tetramethyl derivative* (XI) of the thioether (II) was prepared in the same way as (V) was prepared from (I). It was crystallised from acetic acid in colorless cubes, m. p. 148-49°. (Found: S, 6.4. $C_{20}H_{20}O_6S$ requires S, 6.2 per cent). It showed no coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride.

2:4-Dinitrophenylhydrazone of (II) was obtained as dark red needles, m. p. 284-85° (decomp.). (Found: N, 13.8. $C_{20}H_{20}O_{12}N_2S$ requires N, 13.7 per cent).

2:4-Dihydroxy-5-nitrobenzophenone (XII).—Nitric acid (d 1.4, 5 c. c.) was gradually added to the thioether (II:1 g.), suspended in acetic acid (10 c. c.). After 1 hour, it was diluted with ice and the yellow solid separating was crystallised from alcohol in pale yellow shining needles, m. p. 144-45°. (Found: N, 5.7. $C_{13}H_9O_3N$ requires N, 5.4 per cent). It showed no lowering in m. p. with the nitration product of 2:4-dihydroxybenzophenone, prepared as shown below.

Nitric acid (d 1.4, 50 c. c.) was gradually added to the ice-cooled acetic acid solution of the ketone (10 g.) in the acid (100 c. c.). The mixture was then left at room temperature until the temperature rose to 60°. It was poured over crushed ice and the solid obtained was finally crystallised from alcohol in pale yellow shining needles, m. p. 144-45°. (Found: N, 5.7. $C_{13}H_9O_3N$ requires N, 5.4 per cent). It developed a red coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride solution.

A solution of bromine in acetic acid (7 c. c. of 10%, w/v) was added to the hot solution of 2:4-dihydroxy-5-nitrobenzophenone (1 g.) in acetic acid (10 c. c.). The reaction mixture was kept for 2 hours at room temperature. The yellow solid separating was crystallised from acetic acid in yellow plates, m. p. 208-209°. (Found: Br, 23.4. $C_{13}H_9O_3NBr$ requires Br, 23.7 per cent). It did not lower the melting point of (VIII) described above.

5:5'-Dibromo derivative (XIII) of the thioether (II) was prepared from the latter in the same way as (VI) was prepared from (I). It crystallised from acetic acid in clusters of tiny needles, m. p. 198-99°. (Found: Br, 25.7. $C_{26}H_{10}O_6Br_2S$ requires Br, 25.97 per cent).

The structures assigned to the bromo and the nitro derivatives of 2:4-dihydroxybenzophenone are the most probable ones.